

Unveiling the Use of Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer: An Academic Support in Learning English

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Abstract. This qualitative-phenomenological study explored the experiences of fifteen (15) high school students at Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School concerning using ChatGPT as an academic support in learning English. Employing Collaizi's method of data analysis, the research utilized in-depth interviews and focus group discussions as data collection methods, with fifteen high school student participants chosen through purposive sampling, all with direct experience in using ChatGPT to learn English. The students' experiences were divided into two—the good and bad experiences alike. The former encompasses students' experiences in plagiarism, information accuracy and biases, and the potential of academic dishonesty. At the same time, the latter encapsulates the idea of ChatGPT as a tool to enhance English language learning. Despite these, students expressed that verifying processes from ChatGPT's inputs, understanding topics before ChatGPT's utilization, and using it as a supplementary tool helped them overcome the challenges. The study, however, emphasized the significance of the tool that personalizes students' learning experiences and its benefits in helping non-native English speakers. Lastly, the students' insight that ChatGPT and its AI counterparts need AI literacy for teachers and students to utilize these tools and platforms for their potential to improve learning outcomes. The study recommends that the Department of Education, classroom teachers, and students embrace such tools to adapt to 21st-century learning and innovations, paving the way for further AI tools to improve student outcomes.

KEY WORDS

1. ChatGPT 2. academic support 3. Artificial Intelligence

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1. Introduction

In today's competitive learning set-up, different academic platforms—Artificial Intelligence, for one—have risen. Some are useful, yet few were utilized mindfully. Through such advancement, student work became efficient and trouble-free. ChatGPT, one of the growing AI models in today's age, has benefited different people in all walks of life, especially students. However, ChatGPT presents unique challenges, as it facilitates rapid content generation and raises concerns about plagiarism and academic integrity, particularly in English language learning. Students use such platforms to create essays, poems, academic papers, and other types of paper in just a rapid click. Addressing these concerns is essential for maintaining educational standards and ensuring a fair and enriching learning experience for all students, especially in English. According to Garg et al. (2023), Chat GPT, called

Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer, is a processing tool driven by artificial intelligence that generates projects quickly and easily. In education, Language models powered by artificial intelligence, such as Chat GPT, are effective at finding and fixing grammatical mistakes, enhancing text coherence and clarity, and creating new material (Castillo, 2022). However, Joshi et al. (2023) stated that although ChatGPT has received much favorable attention, it has also caused some trepidation and disorientation in educational settings. There are concerns that students may use ChatGPT to pass exams, take-home assignments, and get good results without gaining knowledge. In a global context, Vietnamese researcher Truong (2023) evaluated that although ChatGPT showcases a biased contribution, it still provides insights into using such models to create educational content, enhance student engagement and interaction, and personalize the learning experience. She added that ChatGPT has a vast and promising impact on education. However, in learning English, there are other problems with AI in education, such as output bias, human oversight, and abuse. If handled effectively, these issues can offer educators new perspectives and chances to introduce pupils to potential social preferences, concerns, and dangers of AI usage (Shamsan et al., 2023). Internationally, Kostka and Toncelli (2023) proved that although AI tools have grown, ChatGPT has altered various fields, possibly because it advanced quickly and is now easily accessible to the public. Although ChatGPT's original purpose was to imitate human interaction, it is capable of much more than that. For example, it can act like anything it can and generate new things like poems, stories, and novels. Subsequently, there are vast ramifications for educators due to ChatGPT's capacity to produce various outputs. On a national level, a news article had been spread in which students from the University of the Philippines Diliman (UPD) were allegedly found using Chat GPT to fulfill their academic requirements. It was verified that the students' work contents were mostly likely written by artificial intelligence (Arasa, 2022). Chowdhury (2023) attested that the model can respond quickly and accurately to various user inquiries since it has been developed on a huge corpus of text data. Although ChatGPT has demonstrated great skills in multiple domains, it has downsides. The model's propensity to generate biased or improper results based on the data it has been built on is one of its key problems. The algorithm might also have trouble with more sophisticated or subtle language tasks because it depends so much on statistical patterns in text data. In the local context, a study conducted by Obenza et al. in Davao City (2024) showed that the use of ChatGPT in higher education is worrisome to students as it can make them overly reliant on the said platform, affecting their critical thinking skills, teamwork, and problem-solving skills. More specifically, the widespread use of ChatGPT at Teofilo V. Hernandez National High School, particularly among upper-level students, is something that the administration worries about and gives rise to legitimate concerns, prompting them to contemplate its integration as a protective measure to uphold academic integrity. While isolated incidents of ChatGPT employment have been reported, the ability of some students to conceal such activities underscores the urgency of the school's commitment to fostering a secure and just learning environment for all. In this backdrop, I discerned conducting a study to delve into this phenomenon and shed light on its implications. Nonetheless, my research aims to know high school students' differing views and experiences by using Chat GPT as an academic support for learning English. Essentially, this study is beneficial for the school in assessing students' knowledge of learning English using Chat GPT as academic support. This will also add new inquiries for educators, students, and the institu-

tion to know students' viewpoints through their lived experiences scrutinizingly. Likewise, this will contribute to the current issues in Philippine education concerning the integration of technological advancement in education and add to related studies that will be conducted in the future.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological study sought to determine the overall experiences of high school students using ChatGPT as academic support for learning English. Also, this research aimed to identify the coping mechanisms extracted from their learning experiences and their insights towards the ChatGPT.

1.2. Research Questions—This study explored the lived experiences of Teofilo V. Hernandez National High School students regarding the usage of ChatGPT as academic support in learning English. It sought to answer the following research questions:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of high school students using ChatGPT as an academic support in learning English?
- (2) How do high school students cope with the challenges brought by using ChatGPT as an academic support in learning English?
- (3) What insights or implications can be gained based on the students' experiences?

1.3. Definition of Terms—Certain words might be unfamiliar in this study. Hence, the following terminologies are defined operationally and conceptually. ChatGPT, or Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer, allows users to ask questions using conversational or natural language. It is a language model that produces text based on the probability of a word occurring based on previous words in the sequence powered by the Internet (Gregersen, 2024). ChatGPT. A natural processing tool driven by artificial intelligence that eases the sweat of individuals in producing information with just a click. English is an academic discipline taught in primary, secondary, and post-secondary education. It encompasses grammar, poetry, literature, oratory, rhetoric, and others (Graff, 2008). English. A school subject area that is part of the current Philippine curriculum that aims to improve students' oral and written skills in English. High School Students. Students in the adolescent stage transition from childhood to adulthood (Torres et al., 2022). High School Students. In this study, students referred to are junior high school students in Grades 7 to 10.

1.4. Significant of the Study—The facts and findings generated by this research will significantly benefit the following group of people: Educational Sector The information gathered in this study will be of substantial significance in global education as it discusses technological advancements and AI and its application to the educational landscape. It will provide further sources to create globally competent solutions. School Heads. This study's findings will also benefit the institution by helping devise new ideas that address speculations regarding the misuse of ChatGPT and other academic platforms in students' academic lives. The institution can also use this study as a reference to heighten further related research. Educators. The information gathered in this study will benefit educators by helping them better utilize ChatGPT in teaching the English language. It may also help them devise strategies for students who use ChatGPT excessively. Students. The results of this research can also benefit students'

awareness of the ChatGPT and its limitations that can affect their learning of the English subject. Future Researchers. This study will serve as a core data set essential in generating new research and improving the current study. Future

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This research study is firmly grounded on the Theory of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis (1989), which aims to illuminate the mechanisms that support technology acceptance to forecast technological behavior and offer theoretical justification for the effective application of technology. By means, it is about the perceived impact of the usage of technological platforms that primarily affects society itself. Relatively, students who use and consume ChatGPT as a main source for inadequate academic activities such as copying generated and verbatim answers might be prone to discern effectiveness negatively. Without prior knowledge and assistance, the excessive use of ChatGPT might cause severe struggles and other plagiaristic maneuver. Additionally, Social Learning Theory, as suggested by Bandura (1977), states that learning occurs through observing the behavior of other individuals through social interaction or so-called socialization. Whether it is direct or indirect, the concept of the theory concerning the use of ChatGPT as academic support in English stipulated that considering the capacity of ChatGPT and its negative effect may have consequences depending on its usage. When used appropriately, students can control their ability to be exposed to generated information. Also, they can learn meaningful English using such a virtual platform. Hence, when misused, they may exhibit a lack of conditioning and take further the idea that ChatGPT is better at producing information than original works. More so, Su Yang (2023) suggested the IDEE framework for applying generative AI or artificial intelligence in Education. IDEE

scholars can obtain solutions or further references to widen this study. Similarly, the knowledge that was contributed would motivate the next researchers to pursue this topic.

comprises identifying the desired outcomes, determining the appropriate level of automation, ensuring ethical considerations, and evaluating effectiveness. The framework considers providing responsive and timely feedback for students who utilize ChatGPT. Also, through this, teachers can tailor their teaching practices by allowing students to be involved in technology usage rather than exposing them without guidance. Using ChatGPT as academic support in English must be proposed with feedback so students know its limitations. Importantly, any activities that require AI sources should follow academic guidelines and be accepted by the school's ethical framework standards. This study leverages the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Social Learning Theory to explore students' experiences with ChatGPT as an academic support tool in learning English. TAM, developed by Davis (1989), focuses on understanding how users accept and use technology. It highlights that students' perceptions of ChatGPT can significantly influence their academic behavior, potentially leading to negative outcomes like plagiarism if not used properly. Bandura's Social Learning Theory (1977) is also applied, emphasizing that learning occurs through observing others. This theory suggests that students' interactions with ChatGPT, whether direct or indirect, shape their learning experiences. Appropriate use of ChatGPT can enhance English learning, while misuse may lead to over-reliance on generated content. Su and Yang's (2023) IDEE framework for integrating AI in education is also considered. This framework outlines steps to ensure AI's ethical and effective use, including setting clear out-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

comes, appropriate automation levels, ethical considerations, and effectiveness evaluations. Presented in Figure 1 is a conceptual framework using a Venn diagram to depict the dynamics of high school students' engagement with ChatGPT as an academic aid in learning English. On the left, it represents students' experiences with ChatGPT, including their challenges, successes, and overall interactions with the tool. On the

right, it illustrates students' coping mechanisms for managing these experiences effectively. The overlapping section in the center symbolizes the insights gained from the intersection of students' experiences and coping strategies. These insights reflect students' reflections and learnings, providing valuable perspectives on using ChatGPT in English language learning.

2. Methodology

This chapter includes an overview of the research design, study participants, data collection process, data analysis strategy, ethical considerations, and standards of excellence upheld by the study. The methodology for this study was comprised of all those mentioned earlier.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study's philosophical underpinnings and qualitative assumptions are essential for guiding the investigation. Ontological, epistemological, axi-

ological, and methodological assumptions form the foundation of qualitative research. These assumptions shape the research design and methodology. According to Creswell (2012), researchers must understand the significance of these assumptions, especially when others have interpreted them within specific frameworks. A paradigm—a set of theories, assumptions, and concepts—influences how researchers view the world and interact with their subjects, impacting their choice of data collection and analysis methods (Alele Aduli, 2023). As Denzin and Lincoln (2018) describe, the philosophical assumptions in research include: Ontology. A fundamental ontological challenge arises in exploring the nature and characteristics of reality. Qualitative researchers acknowledge the existence of multiple realities, with individuals under examination and readers of such studies all subscribing to different perceptions of reality. Consequently, researchers conducting qualitative inquiries aim to capture these diverse realities when studying human phenomena. This involves employing various forms of evidence, such as direct quotations and multiple perspectives, to illuminate multiple realities (Denzin Lincoln, 2018). Thus, in my research, it was imperative to strive towards uncovering universal truths and identifying emerging themes, irrespective of the subjective realities constructed by research participants and the potential interpretations readers might have drawn from the study. Epistemology. Based on the epistemological framework, conducting a qualitative study involves building a strong rapport with participants, leading to the collection of subjective evidence based on personal perspectives. This approach acknowledges that knowledge is derived from the diverse experi-

ences of individuals. In conducting my study, I adhered closely to these epistemological assumptions, ensuring that the research instruments, methods employed, and the evaluation of findings and evidence were thorough and aligned with these principles. Axiology. While all researchers inevitably bring their values to their studies, qualitative researchers are particularly transparent. The foundational principle guiding qualitative research, axiology, prompts an examination of its practical implications. In qualitative inquiry, researchers must openly acknowledge their values, biases, and the inherent subjectivity of the data collected from the field while also recognizing the implicit aspects of the study as a whole. In this research, axiological assumptions shaped ethical considerations and my approach, ensuring adherence to ethical standards and acknowledging the subjectivity inherent in my study's findings. Consequently, I took great care to differentiate between my biases and interpretations and those of the research participants and readers, striving for objectivity in the study's outcomes. Methodology. The methods employed in qualitative research, often called its methodology, are characterized as inductive and emergent, shaped by the researcher's experiences in data collection and analysis. Unlike quantitative research, where logic is typically deductive and theory-driven, qualitative research builds its logic from the ground up, relying less on preconceived theories or the researcher's biases. This methodology encompasses the research inquiries and assumptions, enhancing the precision and solidity of the study's findings. In my study, I drew conclusions based on my research participants' authentic responses, ensuring the results' validity and reliability.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—This study employed a phenomenological framework to explore the comprehensive experiences of high

school students utilizing ChatGPT as an academic aid for learning English. The primary objectives involved uncovering the coping mech-

anisms derived from their encounters and understanding their perspectives on ChatGPT. Embracing phenomenology, this research advocated for a comprehension that transcends surface-level observations. It emphasized the significance of delving into participants' perceptions, emotions, and reflections, acknowledging the varied viewpoints shaped by individual contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). To accomplish these aims, a study emphasizes in-depth interviews,

2.3. Design and Procedure—A phenomenological research design was used in this research study. According to Cropley (2019), the essential tenet of qualitative research is that “truth” is subjective. Every person forms an autonomous, individual picture of the universe, considering their interactions with others and the outside environment. As a result, what an individual—including scholars—takes to be true is just a collection of assumptions, conclusions, and views in that individual’s head. Qualitative research aims to comprehend certain circum-

2.4. Research Participants—A selection of participant sessions was likely necessary to collect quality interview data, as follow-up interviews were conducted throughout the study to clarify and expand participant information (Polking, 2005). Polkinghorne (2005) suggests that participants in qualitative research often number between 10 and 15 people to reach the minimum number of participants in the study. He added that such participants should be rooted in awareness and can shed light on their experiences in a particular phenomenon. Hence, I decided to have 15 research participants in this study, selected from Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School, and have direct experience using ChatGPT as academic support in learning English. However, I have also considered

reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants’ narratives. This approach is designed to capture high school students’ profound experiences, specifically using ChatGPT as an academic support (Murray, 2013). This undertaking aimed to offer valuable insights beyond mere descriptions, providing a deeper understanding of these research participants’ challenges, successes, and perspectives within this specific educational context.

stances better and discover useful knowledge for people to consume (Amorado Talili, 2017). Using the definition of intentionality as the distinguishing attribute, Husserl (2003) also defines phenomenology as the study of the nature of consciousness, especially applied to the individual. Throughout this sense, people’s life experiences ultimately determine all-purpose and significance. Therefore, this qualitative research design allowed me to acknowledge high school students and find their common experiences utilizing ChatGPT.

adding more sets of participants and clarifying research participants’ responses if I needed to exhaust data for the study; however, the number of participants was sufficient. Moreover, the criteria for finding the interviewees were those high school students with at least prior technical knowledge as they are best fit as the research participants of the study, and they are the ones who can give better insights into the phenomenon being studied. Also, I have chosen this school as it has received isolated reports of students using ChatGPT in their academic papers. However, it is imperative to note that I have chosen selected students as research participants who have used it in the past, not concluding they were part of such cases to maintain objectivity.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—The safety of human subjects using suitable ethical norms, as indicated by Arifin (2018), is crucial for any research data. Hence, I followed the ethical conventions and guidelines for qualitative research, with a brief explanation of the ensuing rules and methods I have followed: Social value. This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. From the beginning up until the end of my study, I have always had this perspective that my study would contribute to the larger community as I aimed to solve a particular problem that exists in the larger community in education, which was the growing concern and potential of students using ChatGPT as an academic support in learning English. The data gathered in this study will inform policy and practice in ways that will benefit the educational community I am part of. Informed consent. This describes obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study after providing sufficient information about the study's purpose, methods, potential drawbacks, and benefits. In this research, I ensured that participants fully understood the study and their rights, allowing them to make an informed decision about whether to participate, thereby preserving their autonomy and dignity. Vulnerability of research pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors like age, cognitive ability, socioeconomic status, or health conditions. In this study, I needed to acknowledge and consider prospective participants' potential vulnerability and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involved providing additional protection and support so they would not feel uncomfortable, coerced, or anything at all. Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, these elements are integral to evaluating the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study and implementing measures to safeguard the well-being of participants. In this study, I ensured that the setting where I conducted my study was in a safe, quiet location, away from potential triggers, and participants were assured of my liability for any harm or damages. Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they consent to the disclosure. In the context of this study, I was responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This included anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only, which was me. Also, I guaranteed they would keep any voice records and transcriptions in my vault, and no one had access to them. Justice. This concept relates to the equitable allocation of both the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensured everyone could voice their viewpoints and experiences regardless of age, gender, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status. This involved ensuring that I had research participants from differing backgrounds, that every participant had equal access to attending the interviews I conducted, and that their participation was not burdened. Transparency in research encompasses integrity in every research phase, from conception and execution to reporting results. In this study, I have always been truthful about the research methodologies and the outcomes that came with it. I was open to examination and feedback from my peers, research participants, and mentors to ensure trust, credibility, and accountability within the research community and the general public. The qualification of a researcher relates to one's academic background, professional background, and proficiency in a particular area of study, confirming that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to carry out the research capably. In this investigation, I believed I held suitable qualifications that showcased my

capability to conduct the research, analyze data, and make sense of the results, given that I am taking my extra degree and having attended sufficient training and seminars related to research. The adequacy of facilities in research addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. I guaranteed access to appropriate facilities for conducting my investigation in this research. I ensured we conducted the study in a convenient and secure location and were not staying in a place that we were not allowed to use or enter. I used exclusive notes for this research and platforms and search engines that suit my study. Community involvement in research encompasses the dynamic involvement and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I guaranteed that the research procedure was conducted impartially, objectively, and devoid of personal bias or external influence. I fostered an atmosphere that fostered candid and transparent exploration of concepts and upheld equity in data gathering and analysis. As an expert in qualitative methods, I possess expertise in various techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. My proficiency has allowed me to effectively plan, execute, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that my research questions were adequately addressed and that the results were credible and reliable. As a data collector and keeper, I gathered information from diverse sources, such as interviews or observations, ensuring accurate and secure in-

2.7. Data Collection—The research investigated the experiences of high school students

the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I directly engaged with the people involved, from the research participants to my research adviser, the panel, and my higher-ups. Plagiarism and fabrication. Researchers should strictly follow academic honesty and integrity principles. This entails giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employed tools like plagiarism detectors. I maintained thorough documentation of their research procedures to guarantee that my work was devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries were authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

formation storage. I followed ethical guidelines, safeguarded participants' privacy, and ensured that data was structured and available for later examination and understanding. As a data analyst, I scrutinized the collected data to reveal trends, patterns, and insightful viewpoints aligning with the research question. I employed rigorous qualitative data analysis techniques such as coding and thematic examination to unearth notable discoveries and enhance the understanding within my field of study. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, my responsibility was to condense and articulate the research discoveries succinctly and logically. This included adeptly expressing the study's aims, methods, results, and implications via written materials, speeches, or other dissemination channels. I ensured the research outcomes were accessible and understandable to the intended audience.

using ChatGPT as academic support for learning English. This research sought to identify

the students' coping strategies extracted from their learning experiences and their insights towards the ChatGPT. Elaborated accounts of the methodology are presented as follows: Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School. I commenced the data-gathering stage by securing authorization from the Dean of the Graduate School at the college where the researcher is studying. This involved presenting an official correspondence outlining the research objectives, methodology, and pertinent supporting documents. This task was slated for completion during the final week of September 2023. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. After securing the required endorsement, I sought authorization from the school's division superintendent. This involved submitting a similarly formal letter outlining the research proposal and its relevance to the educational community. Additionally, I included Chapters 1 and 2, along with the research instrument, which detailed the study's objectives and participant identification. Subsequently, I waited for the response from the SDS before initiating the research activities. This was carried out during the first two weeks of October 2023. Asking for permission from the school heads. After I acquired the necessary permission, I secured an endorsement from the school administrators of the selected institutions. This included presenting formal letters of request to each school principal, outlining the research objectives and the expected data collection timeline. I requested permission from the third week of October 2023 to the final week of that month. Obtaining consent from the participants. Having obtained the school administrators' endorse-

ment, I obtained informed consent from the research participants. This involved using informed consent forms that clearly articulated the research's purpose, participant rights, and measures to maintain confidentiality. Consent from the participants was secured in November 2023. Conducting the interview. Once consent was obtained from all participants, I scheduled and conducted interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews occurred during the first two weeks of November 2023. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. After the interview sessions, I transcribed the participants' responses, carefully noting non-verbal cues and relevant contextual details. This process included field notes to thoroughly capture the breadth of participants' reactions. While transcribing the responses, I also periodically consulted my research adviser for guidance. The interviewee's responses were transcribed in the third week of November 2023. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. Subsequently, I engaged in data coding and thematic content analysis. This involved systematically organizing the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes derived from the interview dialogues. Through this process, I derived conclusions and insights regarding the research objectives by identifying patterns and connections within the data. Additionally, I regularly sought professional input and feedback from my adviser to ensure impartial judgment and comprehensive analysis throughout the study. These consultations occurred throughout the study period, focusing on the third to last week of December 2023.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—There were certain essential phases in the examination of phenomenological data. Specifically, I investigated the lived experiences of the high school students who faced using ChatGPT as academic sup-

port and depicted the participants' experiences using Colaizzi's Descriptive Phenomenological Method. According to Colaizzi (1978), as stated by Sanders (2003), the phenomenological method seeks to unveil the genuine essence

of a given phenomenon. His approach comprises seven steps following what I have done in this study. Initially, I engaged deeply with the informants' descriptions to grasp the holistic nature of their experiences; I then distilled significant statements from these descriptions, proceeding to derive underlying meanings from them. These meanings were subsequently or-

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The analytical framework in phenomenological research is a systematic and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I used Colaizzi's method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their experiences in extra-curricular activities. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process offering rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are common, data can also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore their intricate relationships (Wirihana et al., 2018). Data Familiarization. By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I aim to fully understand the meanings conveyed by the participants and gain a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process is crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences. Identifying Significant Statements. I carefully identify every statement in the narratives directly related to the phenomenon I

organized into cohesive themes, which were synthesized to comprehensively portray the phenomenon. From this synthesis, I extracted the essential structure of the phenomenon. Finally, to validate the analysis, informants were consulted to confirm whether the interpretation resonated with their original experiences.

am studying. To identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—must be conducted. This step is essential to ensuring that my analysis stays on topic and provides a strong basis for future thematic development. Formulating Meanings. After carefully examining the important statements, I determine meanings pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admits that complete bracketing is impossible, I must reflexively "bracket" my presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants' real experiences, this process entails putting aside my interpretations as much as is practical. Clustering Themes. I ensure a rigorous analysis that remains true to the participants' experiences by grouping the identified meanings into themes shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. Allowing the themes to naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces preserves the integrity of the analysis. Developing an exhaustive description. I incorporate every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon I write. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon.

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

This step ensures that the final representation presents a comprehensive perspective of each participant’s experiences. Producing the fundamental structure. I break down the lengthy explanation into a succinct statement highlighting the key elements that I believe are crucial to understanding the phenomenon’s structure. This succinct synthesis effectively and concisely communicates the essence of the participants’ experiences, concentrating on the essential components necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. Seeking verification of the fundamental structure. I ask participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflects their experience by returning it to all participants or, in larger studies, to a subsample. I might go back and change the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings are increased, and the analysis is firmly based on the participants’ perspectives.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—This study sought to demonstrate the reliability of conclusions based on third-party evaluations. According to Lincoln and Guba (1985), credibility, confirmability, transferability, and dependability are the four factors that should be considered to generate a reliable study. Credibility. As Polit and Beck (2012) defined, credibility

pertains to the accuracy of information, participants' viewpoints, and the researcher's interpretation and presentation thereof. This concept emphasizes the issue of truth value (Korstjens Moser, 2018), with credibility bolstered by the researcher's personal experiences and participants' affirmation of study conclusions (Cope, 2014). To enhance credibility, I ensured I had prolonged engagements with my research participants regarding the triangulation of my data sources, which enhanced the accuracy and depth of my study's findings. Confirmability. According to Korstjens and Moser (2018), confirmability is focused on the issue of neutrality, where research needs to ensure the inter-subjectivity of the data. According to the data, it can support the study's findings. An audit trail is the technique used in this investigation that was required to provide confirmability. The scientific community is persuaded of the rigor of these investigations by this audit trail, which also helps to verify the validity of qualitative studies (Robinson, 2003). I meticulously documented every data collection and analysis step to maintain confirmability. I ensured transparency and accountability in my research process by keeping an audit trail of my decisions and interpre-

tations. Through member checking, I sought feedback from participants to validate the accuracy and relevance of my findings, enhancing the confirmability of my study. Transferability. It refers to discoveries that may be used in other contexts or with different groups. Hence, the researchers must give a detailed account of the participants and the research methodology to determine whether the findings apply to a given situation (Cope, 2014). In my research, I ensured transferability by meticulously documenting the context, methodology, and characteristics of participants, enabling others to assess the applicability of the findings to their situations. Through detailed and transparent reporting, I aimed to facilitate the transferability of my study's insights to similar contexts or populations. Dependability. Dependability concerns the consistent and stable quality of research results over time. Researchers meticulously record their methodologies, data collection techniques, and analysis procedures to ensure reliability. (Amin et al., 2020; Haq et al., 2023). Hence, I ensured that the data collection methods of my research participants were consistent at different time points using a standardized semi-structured interview.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study deals with the research questions and responses of high school students from Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School concerning their overall experiences with using the ChatGPT as an academic support for learning the English language. Specifically, this research sought to identify the challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights from their learning experiences towards the ChatGPT.

3.1. The lived experiences of High School students using ChatGPT as an Academic Support—Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools such as ChatGPT and its counterparts have emerged as allies for students seeking academic support, particularly in learning English. The ability of AI tools to swiftly aid students in this subject area expedites the learning process, mak-

ing them indispensable aids for language learners. Nevertheless, the integration of such tools into academic settings is not without its ups and downs. Thus, provided below in detail are the experiences of high school students from Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School who encountered utilizing ChatGPT as an academic support in learning English.

3.1.1. Plagiarism—Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School students have found ChatGPT to be a double-edged sword in their English learning journey, with the tool presenting plagiarism-related challenges. While it serves as a valuable resource for generating content and refining language skills, some students inadvertently reproduce ChatGPT-generated text without proper attribution, leading to concerns about plagiarism. From the responses mentioned above, these high school students (S1, S3, S4, S6, S11, S13, and S15) embraced ChatGPT as a resource for handling demanding assignments, appreciating its ability to generate impressive content quickly. However, many faced unexpected consequences, as heavy reliance on ChatGPT led to accusations of pla-

giarism. Teachers became adept at identifying similarities between student work and ChatGPT output, detecting familiar language patterns and structures. Unaware of the potential pitfalls, some students were scolded and tagged for plagiarizing, realizing the importance of proper paraphrasing and referencing. Consistent with the student's responses, Thorp (2023) pointed out that when ChatGPT is used as a co-author in writing, it can produce similar content across multiple articles without proper cross-referencing, leading to self-plagiarism. Basic et al. (2023) corroborated this, showing that students using ChatGPT are more prone to plagiarism than those who do not. Using ChatGPT for plagiarism undermines academic integrity and the fundamental objective of assessments, which is to measure student learning accurately.

3.1.2. Biases and Inaccuracy of Information—Biases and inaccuracies in information were another facet of the ChatGPT experience for Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School students. The vast dataset upon which ChatGPT relies may introduce unintentional biases and inaccuracies in the responses it generates. Students were encouraged to approach the information provided critically, cross-referencing it with reliable sources to validate accuracy. The students (S2, S4, S7, S8, S9, S12, S14) collectively highlighted various concerns with ChatGPT's accuracy and reliability. While S2 emphasized the necessity of skepticism due to occasional inaccuracies, S4 and S12 expressed frustration over outdated information, particularly regarding the release dates of novels. S7 encountered fabricated details, and S8 noted issues

with ChatGPT generating nonsensical terms, complicating information extraction. Also, S9 raised awareness of potential biases in ChatGPT's responses. Lastly, S14 pointed out ChatGPT's indecisiveness and uncertainty, leading to doubts about its accuracy and possible biases. Aligning with participant feedback, Fort Ferrara (2023) contended that bias is prevalent in language models, leading to factual distortions, attribution errors, and misrepresentations. ChatGPT is not immune to these issues, and persistent use may result in discussions veering into irrelevant topics, potentially amplifying the technological capability to generate misleading websites based on its data. Zhou et al. (2023) furthered this, emphasizing that even though chatbot models facilitate human-like conversations, AI models like ChatGPT introduce ethical concerns, prominently the issue of bias.

3.1.3. Potential for Academic Dishonesty—Furthermore, the potential for academic dishonesty loomed as a concern among Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School students using ChatGPT. The tool's accessibility and the ease

with which it generates content tempt some students to engage in practices that compromise academic integrity. According to the student's responses, using ChatGPT for academic tasks without putting in effort (S1) undermined their

critical thinking and integrity in learning. This misuse (S5) contradicted the tool's purpose, as they may rely on generated content without understanding. Additionally, easy access to ChatGPT (S6) tempted students to opt for quick solutions rather than genuine learning, fostering academic dishonesty. Hence, it was crucial to recognize that using ChatGPT as a substitute for personal work (S9) compromised academic integrity and misrepresented true abilities to others. Furthermore, relying solely on ChatGPT without effort (S10) compromised their integrity and devalued the learning experience for themselves and others. Inappropriate engagement with ChatGPT (S14) led to academic dishonesty, and habitual misuse of ChatGPT (S15) fostered this culture, hindering personal growth and intellectual development. Following this, Yu (2023)

3.1.4. Enhancement of learning English— Improvement in English language proficiency has been observed through the utilization of ChatGPT. Despite the hurdles presented to high school students by this tool, they remained steadfast in their belief that it has still played a role in refining their grammatical skills, enhancing writing coherence and clarity, and facilitating the creation of diverse materials such as essays and reports. The challenges encountered serve as stepping stones for overcoming linguistic obstacles, contributing to a more robust understanding of English. According to the students' responses, ChatGPT has been instrumental in transforming how they learned English grammar (S2). By breaking down complex concepts into easily understandable explanations, ChatGPT significantly enhanced their learning efficiency. This improvement extended beyond grammar to writing skills (S4). ChatGPT introduces them to unfamiliar writing concepts, refines sentence structures, enhances vocabulary, and teaches new writing techniques, resulting in noticeable skill enhancement. More-

elucidated that using ChatGPT by students to complete assignments poses a significant risk of fostering academic dishonesty and cheating. This concern has sparked resistance from multiple universities, newspapers, and experts. Conversely, there is a notable amount of opposition and apprehension within academic circles regarding the inappropriate application of ChatGPT in scholarly pursuits. The tool's potential to facilitate dishonest practices in academia has raised concerns among educators and experts alike. Cotton et al. (2024) additionally asserted that students leveraging ChatGPT to produce high-quality work obtain an unfair edge over those without access to the tool. Consequently, ChatGPT's potential to enable plagiarism compromises academic integrity and undermines the true aim of assessments.

over, ChatGPT played a collaborative role in essay development (S6), enriching essays both grammatically and intellectually with suggestions and ideas. The nature of ChatGPT (S8) turned grammar improvement into engaging dialogue, allowing them to participate actively in the learning process. Furthermore, ChatGPT's contribution to vocabulary expansion (S9) is notable, exposing them to diverse linguistic nuances contributing to richer English expression. ChatGPT's continuous availability (S13) as a language companion ensured instant access to explanations and examples during assignments or reading. Despite initial doubts, they highly valued ChatGPT's feedback on writing skills (S15), understanding that effective usage leads to significant improvements over time. In line with this, it is still believed that ChatGPT serves as a valuable tool for enhancing English language learning among students by effectively identifying and correcting grammatical errors, improving text coherence and clarity, and generating new content (Castillo, 2022). In line with the participant's responses, according to Rah-

Fig. 3. The Experiences of High School Students in using ChatGPT as an Academic Support in Learning English

man Watanobe (2023), ChatGPT demonstrates top performance across various applications, including content creation, essay writing, chatbot responses, language translation, question-and-answer functionalities, and programming code, where students can utilize ChatGPT to write essays, describe subjects, and solve complex prob-

lems, thereby expediting their learning process. Figure 3 shows the lived experiences of high school students using ChatGPT as an Academic Support, Plagiarism, biases and inaccuracy of information, enhancement of English learning, and potential for academic dishonesty.

3.2. The coping mechanisms of high school students in using ChatGPT as an Academic Support—High school students navigated their interactions with ChatGPT by employing strategies to enhance their user experience. They utilized this tool as an academic resource

for advancing their proficiency in the English language. This section provides a comprehensive overview of these coping strategies, accompanied by the specific responses of participants, highlighting the themes that emerge from their identified approaches.

3.2.1. Verification Process—First and foremost, students engaged in a meticulous verification process, exercising caution to ensure the accuracy of information obtained from the AI model. Recognizing the potential limitations and occasional inaccuracies inherent in any automated system, students adopted a discerning approach to separate reliable data from speculative content. This critical evaluation involved cross-referencing information with reputable sources, fact-checking, and applying their judgment to assess the credibility of the AI-generated content. Derived from the feedback of the research participants, they have emphasized a consistent practice of fact-checking and cross-referencing information obtained from ChatGPT with reputable sources. Students strategically integrated ChatGPT into their research process, utilizing its insights as a springboard for exploration (S13). While valuing the information from ChatGPT, they cross-referenced it with credible sources to ensure accuracy and depth (S1). This independent fact-checking was habitual to validate the information and cultivate a comprehensive understanding (S2). Before incorporating Chat-

GPT's findings into presentations, students conducted thorough verification through additional research, enriching content with confidence and accuracy (S3). By incorporating ChatGPT into study routines (S9), they reinforced work quality and knowledge breadth by cross-referencing with textbooks and articles. This approach not only upholds academic rigor but also broadens perspectives with diverse viewpoints. Trusting ChatGPT for general knowledge (S10), they also contributed to scholarly discourse by verifying information against scholarly resources, ensuring accuracy and credibility. In accordance with the students' responses, Romero et al. (2023) and Fauzi et al. (2023) mentioned that there should be a verification process for utilizing ChatGPT as a tool in academic settings. The study highlights concerns such as the tool providing incorrect responses, potential impacts on developing essential skills, lack of acknowledgment of intellectual authorship, and sociocultural biases in responses. Verifying the accuracy of ChatGPT's answers before acceptance and strengthening academic ethics and awareness are ways to verify ChatGPT's responses.

3.2.2. ChatGPT as a Supplementary Tool—ChatGPT, according to high school students, should be regarded as a supplementary tool, complementing rather than supplanting essential components of the learning process. While ChatGPT provides insights and support, it is not a substitute for the learning experiences derived from face-to-face engagement, classroom interactions, and individual study efforts. The research participants believed ChatGPT was a valuable tool for enhancing their learning (S1) and engaging with teachers and textbooks for comprehensive understanding (S6). They viewed ChatGPT as an excellent supplement to their studies but not a substitute for the depth gained from real-life experiences and interac-

tions (S5, S10). Students also found ChatGPT beneficial for clarifying concepts but should not replace classroom instruction, discussions, and traditional learning (S11, S15). While ChatGPT provides quick answers and explanations, they stress the importance of not relying on it entirely and continuing to develop critical thinking skills (S14). In line with this vein, Fautzi et al. (2023) pointed out that ChatGPT should be seen as an additional tool for students, not as a replacement for face-to-face engagement or their diligent efforts to learn and succeed in school. Additionally, Al-Worafi et al. (2023) suggested that students and teachers should incorporate ChatGPT into their classroom preparation rather than relying on it entirely to replace their efforts.

3.2.3. Topic Understanding before ChatGPT Utilization—Ultimately, before utilizing ChatGPT, students proactively equipped themselves with a foundational understanding of the topic. This preemptive knowledge ensured that they could critically assess and contextualize the AI-generated responses, enhancing the overall effectiveness of their interaction with ChatGPT as an educational resource. Despite the challenge of inaccurate data and biases, this coping strategy blurred out the potential of relying heavily on ChatGPT. The students' approach to using ChatGPT was highly structured and deliberate. They prioritized familiarity with lessons from English classes to establish a strong knowledge base (S2) and ensured they were well-acquainted with the subject matter before seeking assistance from AI (S4, S9). By thoroughly studying English class lessons beforehand, they approached ChatGPT as a supplementary resource (S7) that enriched their comprehension by integrating AI-generated insights into their coursework (S8). This intentional approach allowed students to engage with

ChatGPT more purposefully, asking targeted questions and gaining additional perspectives after establishing a comprehensive understanding of the material (S10). The students' strategies emphasized the importance of building a solid foundation through traditional learning methods before leveraging AI technologies for further insights and perspectives. Shoufan (2023) solidified the claim of the research participants, who said that students who want to use ChatGPT effectively must have a solid foundation in the subject area to create pertinent prompts and evaluate the system's output. Students without prior knowledge should not depend solely on ChatGPT to study. Hence, ChatGPT should act as an essential tutor, aiding students by summarizing information, assisting with drafts, offering feedback, and answering questions based on the materials they possess (Lo, 2023). Figure 4 shows the coping mechanism for the school heads' challenges in defining their roles and decision-making and the emergence of the three themes: Verification process, ChatGPT as a Supplementary tool, topic understanding before ChatGPT utilization

3.3. The insights of high school students in using ChatGPT as an Academic Support—While students have had their fair share of expe-

riences using ChatGPT as an academic support tool in learning the English language, they have also offered and emphasized insights concerning its usage in the classroom.

3.3.1. ChatGPT personalizes learning experiences—High school students gained a profound insight into the personalized learning experiences facilitated by ChatGPT. Recognizing the capabilities of this AI-driven platform, students observed how ChatGPT tailors its interactions to individual learning styles and preferences. By adapting its responses to user input, the system fosters an engaging and effective educational journey for each student, ensuring that knowledge acquisition aligns with their unique

needs and pace. ChatGPT has transformed the student's learning experience (S3), adapting to their unique style and pace and enhancing their grasp of complex subjects. Moreover, ChatGPT's ability to tailor explanations and create study guides (S6) played a crucial role in the student's exam preparation, aligning perfectly with their academic level. Acting like a knowledgeable study companion (S7), ChatGPT patiently explained difficult topics and nurtured problem-solving skills, making learning more

Fig. 4. The Coping Mechanisms of High School Students in Using ChatGPT as Academic Support in Learning English

engaging. The students also valued ChatGPT's efficiency in summarizing extensive readings (S9), saving time while ensuring understanding across different subjects. Beyond standard textbooks, ChatGPT provides supplementary explanations (S11), encouraging exploration of various topics aligned with the student's interests. Furthermore, for language learning purposes (S14), ChatGPT served as a partner offering practice, grammar correction, and cultural insights, enhancing experience. Finally, ChatGPT's adaptability to diverse learning styles (S15) ensured that explanations were delivered clearly and patiently, addressing the student's needs and surpassing traditional learning resources. Consistent with this, Shoufan (2023)

3.3.2. The Need for Artificial Intelligence Literacy—High school students identified the pressing need for AI literacy, recognizing that understanding artificial intelligence is essential in the modern world. Their insight emphasized the importance of incorporating AI literacy into educational curricula, as students acknowledge that being proficient in AI concepts and applications is crucial for learning in an increasingly AI-driven society. Students expressed and emphasized the benefits of ChatGPT in learning English-related topics. However, they emphasized the need for AI literacy for everybody. Initially skeptical about integrating AI into literature (S2), the students' doubts dissolved as they discovered how ChatGPT enhanced their understanding and collaboration within the literary realm. This transformation occurred as the student's apprehensions about AI potentially overshadowing human storytelling were dispelled (S4), realizing that ChatGPT served as a beneficial tool enriching literary exploration and creativity. Furthermore, their view of writing shifted from being solely human-centered (S5) to perceiving AI like ChatGPT as a collaborative partner, suggesting new perspectives and

asserted that ChatGPT proves advantageous for students' academic pursuits, opening the door to many possibilities. Leveraging its features, students appreciate its intuitive design and life-like responses, enhancing their overall learning experience. Furthermore, ChatGPT enables collaborative learning by generating various scenarios for group activities and provides structured discussions, real-time feedback, and personalized guidance to support group interactions and debates and to create dialogues to aid students in learning English, offering students an interactive and personalized learning environment (Kasneci et al., 2023; Topsakal Topsakal, 2022).

expanding creative boundaries. Despite questioning AI's role in literature (S8), the student found that ChatGPT transformed complex concepts into manageable parts, acting as a personal tutor for deeper literary understanding. Integrating AI like ChatGPT into literary discussions (S9) opened new perspectives, enriching exploration beyond mere technological use. ChatGPT, exemplifying AI's potential (S11), enhances literary analysis by uncovering hidden meanings and acting as a digital companion, enriching the exploration of complex texts. Ultimately, they viewed AI, particularly ChatGPT (S12), as an ever-available resource that transforms literature study into an interactive experience. In alignment with these perspectives, Su and Lai (2023) assert that the introduction of ChatGPT offers both opportunities and challenges for argumentative writing training. Rather than outrightly prohibiting students from utilizing chatbots as writing assistants, there is a call for educators and learners to be equipped with guidance on posing effective questions, employing ChatGPT as a tool for critical thinking and personal growth, and utilizing the technology ethically and effectively. This approach

encourages a shift in focus from skepticism to using ChatGPT to enhance students' writing skills through thoughtful engagement, fostering a balance between technological assistance and nurturing individual writing abilities. Dwivedi

et al. (2023) and Theophilou (2023) also added that while there is the presence of AI in recent days, comprehensive AI literacy is necessary and beneficial for everybody for effective usage techniques and strategies.

3.3.3. AI Helps Non-native English Speakers—High school students gained valuable insight into the supportive role that ChatGPT played for non-native English speakers. Recognizing the challenges individuals face learning English as a second language, students observed how ChatGPT's natural language processing capabilities aid in language acquisition and communication skills. The tool's ability to generate coherent and contextually appropriate responses provides a valuable resource for non-native speakers seeking to improve their English proficiency. High school students, particularly non-native English speakers, have found ChatGPT to be a tool for enhancing their language skills. According to (S1), he found ChatGPT indispensable for improving language skills and confidence through real-time grammar feedback, likening its role to a personal writing assistant. They also praised ChatGPT as an effective learning tool that offers grammar feedback with clear explanations, similar to having a virtual English tutor available 24/7 (S3). ChatGPT's adaptability across writing styles was also highlighted as beneficial for refining language and structure in academic and creative contexts, providing grammar corrections and insightful suggestions (S4). For effective communication in English, ChatGPT was crucial in ensuring clarity and error-free content tailored to academic needs, maintaining a positive school image (S6).

More so, they valued ChatGPT's dynamic feedback for language learning, describing it as conversing with an English expert that accelerates grammar understanding and guides toward native-like expressions (S10). In language exchange sessions, ChatGPT enhanced learning by correcting grammar, providing cultural context, and engaging in conversations like a patient language part (S13). Moreover, ChatGPT was invaluable for the student's literary writing, offering feedback that refines grammar, style, and tone, ultimately elevating their academic work (S15). Accordingly, Moqbel and Al-Kadi (2023) endorsed that sophisticated AI chatbots, exemplified by ChatGPT, can offer extensive support to foreign language learners in their educational responsibilities. Such a language chatbot underscores the importance of reevaluating methods for assessing learning outcomes. Hwang et al. (2023) also added that ChatGPT could support individuals who are not native English speakers. This AI model can serve as a personal, 24/7 English tutor, which is especially beneficial for helping non-native speakers with their writing. Figure 5 shows the coping mechanism for the school heads' challenges in defining their roles and decision-making and the emergence of the three themes: ChatGPT personalizes learning experiences, the need for artificial intelligence (AI), and AI helps native English speakers.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, I present a summary of the study. I derived implications and future directions from the findings summarized here. My research aimed to investigate the experiences, coping strategies, and insights of high school students at Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School who

Fig. 5. The Insights of High School Students in Using ChatGPT as an Academic Support in Learning English

utilized ChatGPT as an academic support in learning English. To achieve my research objectives, I employed a qualitative phenomenological research design. I utilized Collaizi's data analysis tool and approach. In this study, I comprehensively described the experiences shared by high school students in using the said AI tool—ChatGPT—and its role as an academic support in learning English. These students possess valuable knowledge about the phenomenon under investigation, which was thoroughly discussed in the previous chapter.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the experiences of high school students in using ChatGPT as academic support in learning English were biased and information accuracy, plagiarism, and the potential of scholastic dishonesty. Despite these travails, students also believe that ChatGPT has the potential to enhance their way of learning the English language. On the other hand, despite the challenges that high school students encounter while steering the complexities of ChatGPT for academic support in learning English, several commendable coping strategies have emerged. One noteworthy approach involved the implementation of a thorough verification process. Recognizing the potential pitfalls of misinformation, students have learned to cross-reference responses generated by ChatGPT with reliable sources, thereby honing their critical thinking skills and ensuring the accuracy of the information obtained. Another strategic adaptation involved a proactive commitment to understanding the topic before engaging with ChatGPT. By familiarizing themselves with the subject matter beforehand, students enhanced their ability to discern relevant and meaningful insights from the model's responses, fostering a more effective learning experience. Moreover, many students have embraced ChatGPT not as a standalone solution but as a supplementary tool. They integrated its capabilities into their broader learning strategies, combining the strengths of artificial intelligence with traditional study methods to achieve a more comprehensive and well-rounded educational approach. In navigating ChatGPT's challenges, high school students have demonstrated resilience, adaptability, and a proactive commitment to optimizing their learning experiences. Ultimately, high school students have come to appreciate ChatGPT as a transformative tool in their academic journey, attributing significant value to its ability to personalize learning experiences. Recognizing that each student has unique learning needs, they have found that ChatGPT tailors its responses to individual queries, offering a customized approach that enhances comprehension and engagement. Moreover, students have acknowledged the growing importance of AI literacy in the modern educational landscape. Using ChatGPT, they gained subject-specific knowledge and developed crucial skills in interacting with artificial intelligence, preparing them for a future where such literacy is increasingly essential. Additionally, non-native English speakers have found a valuable ally in ChatGPT. Its language capabilities and contextual understanding have proven beneficial in aiding the language acquisition process, providing targeted support and guidance for those navigating the nuances of English as a second language. In embracing these insights, high school students have harnessed the power of ChatGPT as a dynamic and personalized academic companion, promoting a more inclusive and adaptive approach to learning English. In the context of a study examining students' perceptions of using ChatGPT as an academic learning support in English, several theoretical perspectives can provide valuable insights, and social representation theory touches on the research problem being investigated. According

to Moscovici (1984), this theory explores how group interactions and communication shape individuals' thoughts and emotions. This theory helped contextualize how students constructed meanings around ChatGPT as a social object in the study. It considered how students communicated and negotiated shared understandings of ChatGPT within their academic communities. The theory highlighted the symbolic representations and shared comprehension that emerged among students, influencing their attitudes and behaviors towards ChatGPT in the learning context. Also, Georgouli et al.'s framework (2008) also solidified this study. Their framework em-

phasized the multifaceted impact of technology on learning, including administration, content delivery, activities, and community engagement. In the study, this framework guided the exploration of ChatGPT's integration within educational settings. Researchers examined how administrative policies, content delivery methods, interactive activities, and community dynamics shaped students' experiences and perceptions of ChatGPT. These components informed effective strategies for leveraging ChatGPT as a positive learning support tool while addressing potential challenges or misuse.

4.2. Implications—The implications for practice derived from the research study on the experiences of high school students in Teofilo V. Fernandez National High School utilizing ChatGPT as an academic support in learning English, with a qualitative-phenomenological research design and 15 purposively sampled participants, reveal several key recommendations. Firstly, it was crucial to address the issue of plagiarism. Educational institutions should incorporate explicit guidelines and workshops on the ethical use of AI tools like ChatGPT, emphasizing the importance of originality and proper citation. This could be integrated into the curriculum to ensure students are well-informed about plagiarism's potential pitfalls and consequences. Secondly, given the biases and inaccuracies identified in the information provided by ChatGPT, educators should actively engage students in discussions about critical thinking and source evaluation. Incorporating lessons on information literacy, where students learn to question and cross-verify information, would enhance their ability to discern the reliability of AI-generated content. Moreover, the research highlights the positive impact of ChatGPT on learning English. Educators can leverage this finding by integrating AI tools as supplemen-

tary resources in the classroom. Providing guidance on effective utilization and encouraging students to explore ChatGPT within the context of their coursework can enhance language learning experiences. Institutions should establish a verification process for submitted work to mitigate the potential for academic dishonesty. This process should involve discussions and reflections on how students utilized ChatGPT, ensuring transparency and honesty in acknowledging AI assistance. The coping mechanisms identified by students, such as understanding the topic before utilizing ChatGPT and treating it as a supplementary tool, suggest the need for educational interventions. Teachers can guide students on effective study habits, emphasizing the importance of using AI tools as aids rather than substitutes for personal understanding and effort. Additionally, recognizing ChatGPT's role in personalizing learning experiences, educators should explore ways to integrate AI tools into personalized learning plans. This involves tailoring educational content to individual student's needs and preferences, maximizing the benefits of AI in supporting diverse learning styles. Lastly, the insights from non-native English speakers highlight the potential of AI in addressing language barriers. Schools should

consider offering AI literacy programs to enhance students' understanding of these tools and their applications, especially for language learners. In conclusion, the implications for practice center around fostering ethical AI use, promoting critical thinking skills, integrating AI as a supplementary learning tool, establishing verifi-

cation processes, guiding effective coping mechanisms, personalizing learning experiences, and addressing the specific needs of non-native English speakers. These recommendations aim to create a balanced and responsible integration of AI in the educational landscape.

4.3. Future Directions—To further advance our understanding of ChatGPT as an academic support tool among high school students learning English, several recommendations for future research studies emerge. Firstly, there was a critical need for quantitative studies to complement the qualitative findings obtained in this phenomenological research. A quantitative approach could involve conducting large-scale surveys to assess the prevalence of ChatGPT usage, identify patterns of its impact on academic performance, and explore correlations between frequency of use and language proficiency. Additionally, incorporating a mixed-methods design could offer a comprehensive perspective by integrating quantitative data with in-depth qualitative insights, enabling more understanding of the diverse experiences and outcomes associated with ChatGPT use. Expanding the participant pool beyond the current sample would also significantly enhance the generalizability of findings. A more extensive and diverse population, possibly across multiple high schools, could provide a more comprehensive view of how different demographic factors influence the adoption and effectiveness of ChatGPT as an academic support tool. Given the

dynamic nature of technology, a longitudinal study tracking students' experiences over an extended period would capture the evolving impact of ChatGPT on their learning journey. This longitudinal approach could help researchers observe changes in perceptions, academic performance, or ethical considerations over time. Concurrently, exploring the perspectives of educators and administrators alongside student experiences could offer a holistic understanding of the implementation of ChatGPT within the school system. Investigating how educational institutions shape policies around AI tools, providing training for teachers and students, and integrating these technologies into the curriculum would provide valuable insights into the broader academic context. Additionally, future research could delve into designing and evaluating educational interventions to foster responsible AI use. This could involve developing and testing curriculum modules that explicitly address AI literacy, ethical considerations, and strategies for effective and ethical utilization of tools like ChatGPT. These interventions could contribute to developing guidelines for educators and policymakers aiming to maximize the benefits of AI technologies while mitigating potential risks.

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